

Effects of interpersonal trust, team leader support, rewards, and knowledge sharing mechanisms on knowledge sharing in project teams

Wickramasinghe, V.

Widyaratne, R.

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

This paper received “Emerald Literati Network Awards for Excellence 2013 - Outstanding Paper Award”

Citation:

Wickramasinghe, V. & Widyaratne, R. (2012). Effects of interpersonal trust, team leader support, rewards, and knowledge sharing mechanisms on knowledge sharing in project teams. VINE: The Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems, 42 (2), 214 – 236.

This Version is available at: doi: 10.1108/03055721211227255

Purpose- To investigate the effect of interpersonal trust, team leader support, rewards, and knowledge sharing mechanisms on voluntary knowledge sharing in software development project teams in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach- Survey methodology was used and 150 software developers who were directly involved in developing and maintaining a software product from project teams responded. Regression analysis was used for data analysis.

Findings- Interpersonal trust and rewards have significant positive effects on knowledge sharing. Although it was anticipated that the team leader support will be a significant predictor of knowledge sharing, the results did not provide evidence for a positive and significant relationship. “Work-group communications” and “Personal interactions” had significant positive effects on knowledge sharing.

Originality/value- It is expected that the findings of this study will provide useful information to better understand the predictors of the extent of knowledge sharing at the individual level in the context of project teams. By doing so, this exploratory study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Keywords: interpersonal trust, knowledge sharing, knowledge sharing mechanisms, rewards, team leader support.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

An organization's ability to effectively leverage on its knowledge is highly dependent on its people even though it encompasses knowledge enabling platforms (Ipe, 2003). Individuals' knowledge is, therefore, considered as an asset that should be managed effectively to achieve better organisational performance (Andrews and Delahaye, 2000; Bartol and Srivastava, 2002; Refaiy and Labib, 2009) and ultimately to achieve sustainable competitive advantage (Cabrera and Cabrera, 2005; Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). Scholars view knowledge sharing as an organizational innovation, which leads to the dissemination of

innovative ideas that has the potential to improve work processes and to develop new business opportunities (Lin, 2006; Lin, 2008; Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995; Yi, 2009). Although knowledge sharing is a natural function that takes place automatically, it could be very much controlled at the level of individuals (Staples and Jarvenpaa, 2001). For instance, on the one hand, unless the organisation has facilitated the sharing of knowledge that employees use in their daily work activities, it is likely to lose knowledge once employees leave the organisation (Gupta and Govindarajan, 2000; Lam, 2000). On the other hand, even if individuals stay with the organization, the full extent of their knowledge may not be realized and utilized unless opportunities are provided for them to share the knowledge with others in the organization (Weiss, 1999). Therefore, previous research emphasizes the importance of people and people-related factors as critical for voluntary sharing of knowledge in organisations (Andrews and Delahaye, 2000; Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995).

In the context of team work, previous studies provide evidence that knowledge sharing in teams leads to superior team performance in different work environments such as research and development (Berends et al., 2006), new product development (Lee et al., 2010), and software development (Faraj and Sproull, 2000). The literature suggests that the sharing of knowledge in team work settings succeed only if team members actively engage in knowledge sharing and by the efficient management of knowledge for the use by new teams with new projects (Berends et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2010). However, previous studies identify one of the negative aspects associated with these non-hierarchical work teams as members' reluctance to share their knowledge with the others (Cabrera and Cabrera, 2005), and as a consequence the overall performance of the team could deteriorate (Za'rraga and Bonache, 2003).

The current study focused on knowledge sharing in software development project teams. The literature reveals that project teams are made up of members with complementary skills (see Blankenship and Ruona, 2009) and team members are selected by management to work together to complete a specific project or task such as to create a new product or to solve a problem (Wenger and Snyder, 2000). Our review of literature

reveals three important characteristics of project teams. First, project team members have to manage their expertise as the mere presence of expertise on a team is insufficient to accomplish the expected task (see Faraj and Sproull, 2000). In this regard, previous studies found that increased knowledge sharing in project teams may lead to a better utilization of existing knowledge within a team and improved decision making by comprehensive consideration of alternatives (Srivastava et al., 2006). Second, project teams are temporary in nature as team members typically stay together until the specific project or task is completed (Ruuska and Vartiainen, 2005). Therefore, one of the difficult tasks of an organisation is to successfully maintain systems to manage the knowledge that resided within a team because knowledge with the team may be lost when the team disbands (see Blankenship and Ruona, 2009). Third, the work organisation of software development is mainly based on project teams (Faraj and Sproull, 2000). However, the literature identifies software development as a new or aspirant profession and software developers are found to enjoy career advancement through mobility across organisations rather than stick to a single organization (Scholarios and Marks, 2004). While the knowledge of individuals' is critical for the overall team performance and there by for organizational performance, turnover of software developers is expensive not only because of direct costs associated with recruitment, socialisation, and training and development (Mitchell et al., 2001), but also because of indirect costs associated with losing irreplaceable knowledge assets (O'Neill and Adya, 2007). Previous empirical studies continue to provide evidence of poor success rates in software development projects (see Jewels and Ford, 2006) and suggest the importance of better understanding of how to manage software development project teams to increase the chances of success (Faraj and Sproull, 2000). In this regard, scholars (Liebowitz, 2002; Lin, 2006) identify the importance of knowledge sharing and its potential for the retention of knowledge even after employees left the organization. However, our review of literature suggests, on the one hand, only recently attention has been specifically directed towards managing knowledge in project environments (see Bresnen et al., 2003), and on the other hand, little empirical work has been undertaken to investigate various

aspects of knowledge sharing in the context of software development project teams (Faraj and Sproull, 2000; Kotlarsky et al., 2007). Therefore, the available literature provides fragmented insights into the sharing of knowledge in software development projects and offers limited guidance for knowledge sharing practices.

In the above context, this study investigated the influence of interpersonal trust, team leader support, rewards, and knowledge sharing mechanisms on the voluntary knowledge sharing behaviour in software development project teams in Sri Lanka. As reviewed in detail in the section on theoretical background, scholars identify the importance of research concerning different social factors that influence human-centred knowledge sharing (Cronk and Ragsdell, 2008; Rivera-Vazquez et al., 2009; Za'rraga and Bonache, 2003). For instance, previous research has demonstrated the positive effects of interpersonal trust (Costa et al., 2001; Mooradian et al., 2006; Renzl, 2008), rewards (Bartol and Srivastava, 2002; Wolfe and Loraas, 2008), team leader support (Lee et al., 2010; Srivastava et al., 2006), and knowledge sharing mechanisms (Berends et al., 2006; Jones and Borgman, 2007) on knowledge sharing in teams. However, a majority of previous empirical studies include a limited number of social dimensions (e.g. interpersonal trust and leadership) (Lee et al., 2010) in a single study. Therefore, it is reasonable in the current study to analyze several dimensions that may influence the sharing of knowledge within an extended framework. It is expected that the findings of this study will provide useful information for both academics and practitioners to better understand knowledge sharing between individuals in project teams. By doing so, this exploratory study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

Knowledge sharing

Knowledge sharing is the act of knowledge provider making knowledge available to others within the organization (Ipe, 2003; Mooradian et al., 2006; Szulanski, 1996). Szulanski

(1996) stated that knowledge sharing is not a two-way knowledge exchange between knowledge providers and knowledge recipients and knowledge sharing is limited only to the behaviour of knowledge providers. Teng and Song (2011) suggested that knowledge sharing can be either solicited or voluntary, where solicited knowledge sharing is referred to the sending and receiving of requests for knowledge, as well as the subsequent fulfilment of these requests while voluntary knowledge sharing is referred to the sending and receiving of knowledge without any prior solicitation. However, Davenport (1997) identified knowledge sharing as a voluntary act, where the term knowledge sharing implies that provider voluntarily presents knowledge in a form that can be used by others and it involves some conscious action on the part of the provider who possesses the knowledge and actively participates in the sharing process even though there is no compulsion to do so. Following the arguments made by Davenport (1997), in the current study the term knowledge sharing is used to refer to the voluntary provision of knowledge by those who possess the knowledge to other members in the team.

Lowendahl et al. (2001) identified three types of knowledge that individuals share, namely know-how, know-what, and dispositional knowledge. According to Lowendahl et al. (2001) know-how includes experienced-based knowledge that is subjective in nature, know-what includes task-related knowledge that is objective in nature, and dispositional knowledge includes an individual's talents, aptitude, and abilities. Leinonen and Bluemink (2008) found that team members evaluate what knowledge is shared between them. Leinonen and Bluemink (2008) suggest that the distributed team members' presumed shared knowledge did not focus directly on the content of the shared project task. Instead, they suggest that the distributed team members' presumed shared knowledge focuses on how collaborative the distributed working processes are and what is the common goal. Further, Leinonen and Bluemink (2008) suggest that in order to construct new knowledge collaboratively the distributed team members had a need to explain their shared common frame of reference to coordinate their work. Hence, for the successful sharing of knowledge, interaction and communication among team members is vital (Cohen and Bailey, 1997). Faraj and Sproull

(2000, p. 1554), in the context of software development, suggest the importance of coordination of expertise about who knows what in the team by stating that “teams must be able to manage their skills and knowledge interdependencies effectively through expertise coordination, which entails knowing where expertise is located, knowing where expertise is needed, and bringing needed expertise to bear”.

Previous empirical studies on knowledge sharing operationalized the term knowledge sharing differently. For example, Liebowitz (2002) provides evidence for the use of several measures to explain an individual’s sharing of knowledge such as counting the number of hits on personal postings, the number of documents submitted, the number of contributions to meetings, the number of written reports, the rate of contribution to knowledge data bases, the number of new ideas, the number of improvement suggestions made, and the number of presentations made. In this regard, although computer-based knowledge sharing is relatively easier to track other forms of knowledge sharing taking place through informal conversations and personal networks are difficult to monitor but may have a considerable impact on organizational performance (see Yi, 2009). To overcome this difficulty some researchers tried to quantify knowledge sharing by asking employees how often they shared work experience, expertise from education and training, and business knowledge obtained informally with others in the team (Lee, 2001). However, scholars (Yi, 2009) argue that such a listing and rating of knowledge dimensions do not constitute different knowledge sharing behaviours. In line of these arguments, several researchers attempted to measure knowledge sharing behaviour by inquiring individuals how frequently or how well they share knowledge with other members (Faraj and Sproull, 2000; Yi, 2009; Za’rraga and Bonache, 2003). Some other researchers attempted to measure individuals’ willingness or intention to share knowledge (Bock et al., 2005; Reychav and Weisberg, 2010) by operationalizing the intention of knowledge sharing as the degree of one’s positive feelings about sharing one’s knowledge. In this regard, Choi et al. (2008) investigated the relationship between knowledge sharing intention and knowledge sharing behaviour and empirically found a strong positive association between knowledge sharing intention and behaviour.

Knowledge sharing mechanisms

The literature reveals that the availability of several different knowledge sharing mechanisms and the richness of these mechanisms influence the effectiveness of knowledge sharing behaviour (Berends et al., 2006; Jones and Borgman, 2007). Some of the commonly used mechanisms for knowledge sharing are brainstorming and collaborative problem solving (Berends et al., 2006; Huang and Newell, 2003), team work (Al-Alawi et al., 2007; Garrett and Caldwell, 2002), Storytelling (Fong and Chu, 2006), training (Al-Alawi et al., 2007), informal chatting (Al-Alawi et al., 2007; Fong and Chu, 2006; Newell et al., 2006), meetings, project briefing and reviewing sessions (Fong and Chu, 2006), and information technology based mechanisms such as teleconferencing, newsgroups, e-mail, Wikis, web-based discussions, and knowledge sharing boards (Fong and Chu, 2006; Hall, 2001; Jones and Borgman, 2007). Some scholars compared the effectiveness of knowledge sharing mechanisms (Newell et al., 2006) and concluded that informal person to person knowledge sharing is more effective than technology based mechanisms in sharing knowledge in project teams.

The literature provides evidence that there are variations in the usage of knowledge sharing mechanisms across different parts of the world. For instance, in a comparative study conducted in Hong Kong and in the UK construction industries, Fong and Chu (2006) provided evidence that in the Hong Kong construction industry the mostly used mechanisms are meetings, phone calls, teleconferencing, informal chatting and story telling where as newsgroups, web-based discussions, knowledge sharing boards, and the Internet are seldom in use. However, Fong and Chu (2006) provided evidence that in the UK construction industry the mostly used mechanisms are informal chatting, story telling, followed by phone calls and teleconferencing, and meetings where as knowledge sharing boards, newsgroups and web-based discussions had never being used. Jones and Borgman (2007) found that the greatly used mechanisms by the top executives from several industries in the USA are e-mail and knowledge repositories while discussion forums are the least in

use. Further, in the context of Bahrain public and private sectors, Al-Alawi et al. (2007) found collaboration and teamwork as the greatly used mechanisms for knowledge sharing.

Some scholars suggested classifying different knowledge sharing mechanisms into broad categories (Bartol and Srivastava, 2002). For instance, Bartol and Srivastava (2002) classified the mechanisms into four categories namely, individual contribution to databases, formal interactions within and between teams, knowledge sharing across work units, and knowledge sharing through informal interactions.

Overall, the above reviewed literature provides evidence for the existence of several different mechanisms to facilitate the sharing of knowledge from source to target, which provide convenience and flexibility in terms of time and place. Further, the literature reviewed above indicates that all the knowledge sharing mechanisms do not have a similar impact on the extent of knowledge sharing. However, it should be noted that our review of literature has not been able to find any studies that addressed the influence of knowledge sharing mechanisms on the extent of knowledge sharing in project teams or in the software development industry, in particular. Consistent with the past research, it is hypothesised for this study:

Hypothesis 1: Knowledge sharing mechanisms will have a significant positive effect on knowledge sharing.

Interpersonal trust

Trust relates to the expectation of honest and cooperative behaviour in others' future actions (Fukuyama 1995; Mayer et al., 1995). For instance, Fukuyama (1995, p. 26) defined trust as "the expectation that arises within a community of regular, honest and cooperative behaviour, based on commonly shared norms, on the part of the members of the community". Some others argue that trust entails a state of perceived vulnerability or risk that is derived from individuals' uncertainty regarding the motives, intentions, and prospective actions of others on whom they depend (see Kramer, 1999). For instance, Mayer et al. (1995) defined interpersonal trust as "the willingness of a party to be vulnerable

to the actions of another party based on the expectation that the other will perform a particular action important to the trustor, irrespective of the ability to monitor or control that other party” (Mayer et al., 1995, p. 712). Further, Kramer (1999) argues that trust needs to be conceptualized not only as a calculative orientation toward risk, but also a social orientation toward other people and toward society as a whole. Hence, one can have trust in a person, in a system or in collectivity (see Ipe, 2003).

Interpersonal trust is identified as a necessary prerequisite for knowledge sharing (Al-Alawi et al., 2007; Costa et al., 2001; Holste and Fields, 2010; Lin, 2006; Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). The willingness to share knowledge is higher when individuals trust and identify with one another (Cabrera and Cabrera, 2005; MacNeil, 2003). Nonaka (1990) observed that interpersonal trust eliminates deception, cheating, and tendency among employees to blame others for organizational failures. Andrews and Delahaye (2000) concluded that in the absence of trust, formal knowledge sharing practices are insufficient to encourage individuals to share knowledge with others. In this regard, Choi et al. (2008) found that trust is more important than technical support in facilitating knowledge sharing. Although a majority of the past studies report significant positive relationship between trust and knowledge sharing, Kim and Lee (2006) had not found a statistically significant association between trust and employee knowledge sharing. However, that study was not conducted in the context of team work. Further, in the context of knowledge sharing in a military organization, Friesl et al. (2011) found that knowledge sharing is influenced by suspicion, which is based on a lack of understanding of the objectives of a new initiative, rather than a lack of trust in the organization.

Several past research studies were conducted on knowledge sharing in team work environment and empirically found that interpersonal trust positively associate with knowledge sharing (Renzl, 2008; Za´rraga and Bonache, 2003). For instance, Za´rraga and Bonache (2003) found that the most important component explaining the degree of sharing of knowledge in work teams is mutual trust. Whitener et al. (1998) argue that team members with stronger trust are more likely to work together collaboratively and conscientiously.

According to McAllister (1995) trust involves mutual care and concern between workers as well as co-worker reliability and competence. When team members trust each others' capabilities and competencies they share information more freely (Zand, 1972), they coordinate knowledge among team members more effectively (Weick and Roberts, 1993), and the information shared is higher in quality (Bernhardt and Ragsdell, 2006; Zand, 1972).

Few research studies have been conducted on knowledge sharing in project teams and found that interpersonal trust in the team significantly predicts the extent of team knowledge sharing (Lee et al., 2010). In one of such studies, Costa et al. (2001) state that trust in the team is of great importance for project work as team members are often reliant on their colleagues than on the leader for performance and satisfaction. In the context of project teams, which are temporary in nature, Ipe (2003) suggests that prior connections between team members is an important determinant in the development of initial trust and for effective teamwork in the course of the project. In this regards, Kramer (1999) argues that the size and degree of social and structural differentiation found within most organizations precludes the sort of repeated interactions and dense social relations required for the development of personalized trust. Yet, Kramer and Lewicki (2010) argue that role-based knowledge could become a basis for positive expectations about others, in so far as those expectations are predicated on knowledge that individuals occupy particular roles in the organization. According to Kramer (1999, p. 578), to the extent that people within an organization have confidence in the fact that role occupancy signals both an intent to fulfill obligations and competence in carrying them out, individuals can adopt a sort of presumptive trust based upon knowledge of role relations even in the absence of personalized knowledge or history of prior interaction.

On the basis of our reading of the literature reviewed above that indicates interpersonal trust influences the extent of knowledge sharing, it is hypothesised:
Hypothesis 2: Interpersonal trust will have a significant positive effect on knowledge sharing.

Team leader support

The literature reveals the importance of a variety of leader behaviours in knowledge sharing (Srivastava et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2010). Several previous research studies have empirically demonstrated a positive direct effect of team leadership on team knowledge sharing (Lee et al., 2010; Srivastava et al., 2006; Za'rraga and Bonache, 2003). Srivastava et al. (2006) state that knowledge sharing does not happen automatically in a team, and the team's leader has a pivotal role to play in making it happen.

The literature on team leadership suggests that team leadership can be conceptualized as a set of roles involved in managing tasks and functions such as organizing, envisioning, spanning, knowledge building, and social maintenance that are essential for team performance (Barry, 1991; Bain et al., 2005). According to Eppler and Sukuowski (2000) the team leader must not only coordinate the different viewpoints found within the team but also provide guidelines for the team and provide real and virtual spaces for communication. Eppler and Sukuowski (2000) further state that team leader's function is to serve as a collaborator for openly sharing team information, put team members in others' shoes, provide feedback and create a climate of 'high care'. According to Srivastava et al. (2006) and Bain et al. (2005) knowledge sharing in a team is not automatic, and the team's leader has the potential to strongly influence the extent of knowledge sharing. Bain et al. (2005) state that team leader should provide advice on technical issues, develop the team's expertise, monitor the quality of the team's work and initiate new approaches to team tasks. Empowering team leadership is found to improve employee's job autonomy, which is essential for team members to undertake conscious, voluntary knowledge sharing (Bennis and Townsend, 1997).

In the context of software development project teams, previous studies found that team performance is linked to the effectiveness of teamwork coordination (Faraj and Sproull, 2000; Kraut and Streeter, 1995; Nidumolu, 1995, Walz et al., 1993). For instance Walz et al. (1993) identified breakdowns in team coordination and integration as a key factor that hinder the achievement of project outcomes in software development project teams, which implies the importance of the team leader.

On the basis of our reading of the literature reviewed above that indicates team leader support influence the extent of knowledge sharing, and preliminary investigations made by us about software developers in software development firms in Sri Lanka, it is proposed that team leader support will influence the extent of knowledge sharing. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 3: Team leader support will have a significant positive effect on knowledge sharing.

Rewards

Organizational rewards are identified as useful in motivating individuals to perform desired behaviours (Bartol and Locke, 2000). Such rewards range from monetary incentives such as increased salary and bonuses to non-monetary rewards such as promotion and job security (Hall, 2001). Previous research provides evidence that real or perceived rewards encourage employees to share their knowledge (Al-Alawi et al., 2007; Gupta and Govindarajan, 2000; Hall, 2001; Ipe, 2003; Lin, 2007). For instance, Choi et al. (2008) provide evidence that reward mechanism is more important than technical support in facilitating knowledge sharing. Bartol and Srivastava (2002) suggest that monetary rewards could encourage knowledge sharing through individual contribution to databases, formal interactions within and between teams, and knowledge sharing across work units. However, according to Bartol and Srivastava (2002) knowledge sharing through informal interactions has to be rewarded by intangible incentives such as recognition. However, Wolfe and Loraas (2008) found that incentives can promote knowledge sharing regardless of its type (e.g. monetary or nonmonetary). Some previous studies suggest that knowledge sharing is most likely to occur when individuals perceive that incentives they receive exceed their perceived costs (see Bock et al., 2005). Wolfe and Loraas (2008) found that individuals may perceive the incentives provided for knowledge sharing as sufficient only if those addressed individuals' self-determined incentive sufficiency. Therefore, they suggest the need of monitoring individuals' perceived incentive sufficiency in designing incentive programmes to facilitate

knowledge sharing. In a study that investigated whether financial incentives increase knowledge sharing in a computer mediated environment, Taylor (2006) found that group financial incentives inspired more knowledge sharing than did either tournament or piece-rate incentives. Kim and Lee (2006) found that performance-based reward systems significantly affect employee knowledge-sharing in the context of both public and private sector organizations.

Although a majority of previous empirical research support that rewards and knowledge sharing are positively correlated as reviewed above, some studies have shown that rewards are insufficient (Jewels and Ford, 2006; McDermott and O'Dell, 2001) for knowledge sharing. For instance, McDermott and O'Dell (2001) suggest that professionals share knowledge mainly to have a sense of involvement and contribution than receiving any other form of rewards. In a comparative study conducted in Hong Kong and in the UK construction industries, Fong and Chu (2006) provide evidence that the practitioners in the UK construction industry share knowledge mainly for the benefit of others in the firm, but not for monetary returns. Further, according to Fong and Chu (2006) in Hong Kong construction industry one of the less critical factors for knowledge sharing is rewards. Jewels and Ford (2006) also found that financial rewards and perceived drop in status had the least impact on individuals' intentions to share knowledge in information technology (IT) projects. Lin (2007, p. 145) investigated the effect of rewards on knowledge sharing and also found that rewards did not significantly impact on employee attitudes and behaviour intentions of knowledge sharing. They, therefore, suggest that organizations desiring to encourage knowledge sharing between individuals should not emphasize organizational rewards (such as salary incentives, bonuses, promotion incentives, or job security) as a primary knowledge sharing mechanism because such rewards secure only temporary compliance. Contrary to common belief, Bock et al. (2005) found that anticipated rewards exert a negative effect on individuals' knowledge sharing attitudes. Therefore, based on the literature reviewed above, the influence of rewards on knowledge sharing is mixed. Cabrera and Cabrera (2005), in this

regard, suggest that the recognition of knowledge sharing by way of rewards should be done with great care.

Consistent with the majority of findings of the past research that indicate employees who perceive that they can receive rewards by sharing knowledge will be more inclined to share their knowledge, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 4: Rewards will have a significant positive effect on knowledge sharing.

Figure 1 shows the hypothesised research model.

Take in Figure 1

Methodology

Sample

A random sample of software developers full-time engaged in software development firms was selected. There were about 40 software development firms with more than 100 employees operating in the country. This restriction on the number of employees was imposed to eliminate small firms where job categories are not explicit. A contact person was identified at each firm. Contact persons were asked to randomly identify software development project teams whose main job function is development and maintenance of a software product from his/her firm and distribute the self-administered survey questionnaire. Contact persons were instructed to select about 2-3 members who were directly involved in developing and maintaining a software product from each project team. Of the 320 questionnaires sent out, 150 valid responses were returned, yielding a response rate of 47% of the original sample. The characteristics of the sample are shown in Table 1.

Take in Table I

When the sample characteristics shown in Table 1 are compared with the labour force statistics of Sri Lanka, of the total 7.5 million labour force of the country, 65% were male. 13% of the labour force belonged to the age group of 15–24 years, 36% belonged to the age group of 25–39 years and 51% belonged to the age group of over 40 years. With regard to the educational attainment of the labour force, 16% had General Certificate in Education (Ordinary Level) that equals to 10 years of education, and 16% had General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level) that equals to 13 years of education (Department of Census and Statistics, 2008). When the sample characteristics shown in Table 1 are compared with IT work force statistics of Sri Lanka, since the mid 1990s the country witnessed a growth of IT firms and there are approximately a 30,000 member IT workforce. 45% of the IT work force has a bachelor's degree or a higher qualification in IT (SLICTA, 2007). Published secondary data on the population characteristics of software developers or IT work force are difficult to be found in Sri Lanka. However, the demographics of the sample of our study do not show a deviation from the details of the sample characteristics depicted in SLICTA (2007).

Measures

All the variables were measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). For all measurement scales, standardised Cronbach's alpha was examined and principal components factor analysis (varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7. The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct (refer to Table I).

The extent of knowledge sharing by team members was measured by the four-item scale from Faraj and Sproull (2000). They developed and used this scale for a study on software

development project teams. This scale has also been used in prior research by Srivastava et al. (2006) in the context of knowledge sharing in teams and found to be valid and reliable. Example items include “People in our team share their special knowledge and expertise with one another” and “More knowledgeable team members freely provide other members with hard-to-find knowledge or specialized skills”. In our study, factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha = 0.733, Eigenvalue = 1.96, and explained variation =65.21 percent.

Interpersonal trust was measured by the three-item scale from Cook and Wall (1980). This scale has been used in prior research by Mooradian et al. (2006) in the context of knowledge sharing in software development and found to be valid and reliable. Example items include “I can trust the people I work with to lend me a hand if I needed it” and “If I got into difficulties at work I know my colleagues would try and help me out”. In our study, factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha = 0.761, Eigenvalue = 1.39, and explained variation =69.48 percent.

Team leader support was measured by the four-item scale from Za’rraga and Bonache (2003) which was used in the context of knowledge sharing in teams. Example items include “I can obtain from the leader of my team all the information I need to carry out my day-to-day work” and “The leader of my work team encourages a climate of trust and co-operation among the members of the team”. In our study, factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha = 0.815, Eigenvalue = 1.69, and explained variation =84.38 percent.

Perception towards rewards associated with knowledge sharing was measured by the six-items from Choi et al., (2008). This scale covered both extrinsic outcomes (e.g. promotions and monetary gains) and intrinsic outcomes (e.g. gaining visibility, increased reputation, professional pride in being recognized as an expert, finding it rewarding when others use

one's ideas) of knowledge sharing. Example items include "The more I share my own knowledge, the more my reputation would be enhanced" and "When I share my knowledge, I can get more chance of promotion". In our study, factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach's alpha = 0.787, Eigenvalue = 2.10, and explained variation =70.14 percent.

Knowledge sharing mechanisms were measured by asking the participants how frequently they use different mechanisms to share their knowledge. A 13-item list of knowledge sharing mechanisms that can be used by individuals was generated from preliminary inquiries made by us in the Sri Lankan industry and from the review of the existing literature (such as Berends et al., 2006; Jones and Borgman, 2007; Yi, 2009). In analyzing the responses for knowledge sharing mechanisms, a frequency distribution was produced to check on the methods used. Our analysis showed that 13-item measure had standardized Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.813. Principal-components factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 73 per cent (72.95) of the variance. Of these three factors, Factor 1 was labelled as "Work-group communications", Factor 2 as "Personal interactions", and Factor 3 as "Publications, seminars and workshops". Table II summarizes the results of the factor analysis.

Take in Table II

The literature suggests that individuals' perceptions may vary by their demographic characteristics, such as gender, age, or tenure (Bock et al., 2005) and firm specific characteristics such as firm size (in terms of number of employees) and industry sector (Jones and Borgman, 2007). Therefore, three individual demographic characteristics (age, gender, and tenure), one group characteristic (number of team members), and two firm level characteristics (number of employees and years of industry presence) were controlled in the

analysis. In other words, in evaluating the effect of interpersonal trust, rewards, team leader support, and knowledge sharing mechanisms on the level of knowledge sharing, the study controlled for six other variables that could effect the level of knowledge sharing. By holding these variables constant, the analysis could isolate whether there actually is a relationship between the level of knowledge sharing and interpersonal trust, rewards, team leader support and knowledge sharing mechanisms making the findings more powerful and “true”. Therefore, it is expected that after controlling for these six variables, the variables of interpersonal trust, rewards, team leader support, and knowledge sharing mechanisms each make an individual contribution in predicting the level of knowledge sharing; increase in overall R^2 to increase power or estimate change in an outcome variable. Therefore, to assess the effect of control variables, these six control variables were entered in the first step of the regression equation, followed by the predictor variables of interpersonal trust, rewards, team leader support, and knowledge sharing mechanisms in the subsequent step. A statistical test of the change in R^2 from the first stage is used to evaluate the importance of interpersonal trust, rewards, team leader support, and knowledge sharing mechanisms in predicting the level of knowledge sharing. In the analysis, gender was coded as female = 0, male = 1; the number of employees in the present workplace was coded as less than 500 = 0, more than 500=1. The values for age, the years of experience in the present workplace, the number of team members in the team and the years of industry presence were log transformed.

Methods of data collection

Considering the literacy of the respondents and amenability of the research questions, the self-administered survey questionnaire was in the English language. It was pre-tested with a random sample that fitted with the intended sample of the study prior to the distribution.

When self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature highlights the problem of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003; Spector,

1994). However, Spector (1994) suggests that despite the weaknesses of the cross-sectional self-report methodology, this design can be quite useful in providing a picture of and inter-correlations among people's job environment and their reactions to jobs and for deriving hypotheses. Therefore, procedural and statistical measures were taken to reduce common method bias in the current study. First, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension (a procedure recommended by Podsakoff et al., 2003). Second, factor analysis was used to conduct Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff et al. (2003).

Results

The means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations for the study variables are shown in Table III. The correlation between interpersonal trust and rewards and the extent of knowledge sharing are positive and significant. Further, correlations between two factors of knowledge sharing mechanisms, i.e., work-group communications and personal interactions and the extent of knowledge sharing are positive and significant.

Take in Table III

To test our expectations, regression coefficients and significance levels were calculated controlling for the six control variables as mentioned above. Results are summarized in Table IV.

Take in Table IV

According to the model summary shown in Table IV, control variables are not significant in predicting knowledge sharing (Adj. R² = 0.048, p>0.05). The final model explained 47% of

the variance in the extent of knowledge sharing (Adj. R2 = 0.466, $p < 0.001$). The main variables of interpersonal trust, rewards, team leader support and knowledge sharing mechanisms alone explained 42% (R^2 Change = 0.424, $p < 0.001$) of the variability of knowledge sharing. Interpersonal trust has a significant positive effect ($\beta = 0.493$, $p < 0.001$) on knowledge sharing, supporting H1. Rewards have a significant positive effect ($\beta = 0.269$, $p < 0.05$) on knowledge sharing, supporting H2. It is expected in H3 that team leader support will have a significant positive effect on the extent of knowledge sharing. However, the results of the analysis do not support H3. It is expected in H4 that methods of knowledge sharing will have a significant positive effects on the extent of knowledge sharing. The results shown in Table VI suggest that work-group communications ($\beta = 0.294$, $p < 0.01$) and personal interactions ($\beta = 0.169$, $p < 0.05$) have significant positive effects on knowledge sharing. However, “publications, seminars and workshops” did not have a significant positive effect on the extent of knowledge sharing. Hence, H4 is partially supported. The results also suggest that none of the control variables had significant effects on the extent of knowledge sharing.

Discussion, conclusions and implications

The purpose of the current study was to enhance the understanding of knowledge sharing in project teams in the context of software development projects. The study investigated the relationship between the extent of knowledge sharing and interpersonal trust, rewards, team leader support, and knowledge sharing mechanisms.

It was found that the extent of knowledge sharing between team members is high (mean= 4.17), the level of trust in peers is high (mean= 4.00), perceptions toward rewards associated with knowledge sharing is moderate (mean= 3.04), and team leader support is high (mean= 3.70). With regard to the mechanisms frequently used in sharing knowledge, it was found that “brainstorming and collective problem solving” (mean = 4.62) was the most frequently used while the least used was workshops. In this regard, Al-Alawi et al. (2007) state face-to-face communication is the best way of sharing knowledge. As suggested by

Walsham (2001), the electronic communication methods have obtained a higher mean scores implying frequent usage. The factor analysis derived three factors for knowledge sharing mechanisms, namely, work-group communications, personal interactions, and publications, seminars and workshops. The factor “work-group communications” consisted of mechanisms such as social bookmarking and brainstorming and collective problem solving. The factor “personal interactions” consisted of mechanisms such as Wikis, e-mails, and chatting. The mean values shown in Table II suggested that the most frequently used mechanisms for knowledge sharing is personal interactions, followed by work-group communications.

The study investigated the relationship between the extent of knowledge sharing and interpersonal trust, rewards, team leader support and knowledge sharing mechanisms. It was found that interpersonal trust has a significant positive effect on knowledge sharing. This finding supports the findings of the previous research (Costa et al. 2001; Lee et al., 2010) that found interpersonal trust as an important predictor of knowledge sharing in the project team work environment. With regard to the relationship between rewards and knowledge sharing, it was found that perceived rewards associated with knowledge sharing have a significant positive effect on the extent of knowledge sharing. This finding supports the findings of previous research (such as Al-Alawi et al., 2007; Fong and Chu, 2006; Ipe, 2003; Lin, 2007). Although some previous studies (Jewels and Ford, 2006; McDermott and O’Dell, 2001) found that rewards do not have a significant impact on knowledge sharing, our study provide evidence for positive and significant effect of rewards on knowledge sharing. Further, the findings of our study do not support the findings of Bock et al. (2005), who found that rewards have a negative effect on knowledge sharing.

Previous research (such as Barry, 1991; Bain et al., 2005; Srivastava et al., 2006) provided evidence that team leader support is significant for the extent of knowledge sharing in teams. Therefore, we have anticipated that the team leader support will be a significant predictor of knowledge sharing in our study. However, the results did not provide evidence for a positive and significant relationship. However, it should be noted that we have not come

across previous empirical studies that investigated the team leader support in the context of software development projects. Although few studies have been conducted on the importance of team work coordination (e.g Faraj and Sproull, 2000; Kraut and Streeter, 1995; Nidumolu, 1995, Walz et al., 1993) it is very rare to find empirical studies that investigated the relationship between team leader support and knowledge sharing in software development projects. Possible explanations for the insignificant relationship between team leader support and knowledge sharing in our study are, first, team members may perceive that in carrying out day-to-day work tasks the sharing of knowledge is natural and they have to willingly and consistently share their knowledge (see McDermott & O'Dell 2001). Second, in the software development projects, knowledge sharing networks are built on existing networks that team members use in their daily work. Third, in the project team environment, jobs are designed to encourage collaboration, interdependency and cross-functional interactions among team members (Lin, 2006). Fourth, as stated by Costa et al. (2001) team members may be reliant on their colleagues than on the leader for performance and satisfaction. These characteristics eventually provide awareness to team members on why share, what to share, when to share, and how to share and who to share with. However, MacNeil, (2003) states that there is an agreement in the academic literature concerning the importance of the role of leader in teams. One can, therefore, argue that in the project team context too, team leader's role is important to provide knowledge support during job execution, to reflect on lessons learned to improve individual learning and to contribute to organizational learning (see Small and Sage, 2006). In this context, it is also possible to argue that team members may realise the importance of team leader support once it is absent. However, to test this assumption future research could be designed to examine software development teams which have had less team leader support. Therefore, more future research studies in different samples are necessary to validate the relationship found in this study.

Of the three knowledge sharing mechanisms, work-group communications and personal interactions (such as Wikis, e-mails, and chatting) had significant positive effects on

knowledge sharing while publications, seminars and workshops did not have significant positive effect on knowledge sharing. Work-group communication mechanisms (such as bookmarking and brainstorming and collective problem solving) facilitate project team members to keep each other informed on the progress of the sub-problems the team is working on as well as to share questions, suggestions and instructions required in completing tasks of the project (see Berends et al., 2006). With regard to personal interactions (such as Wikis, e-mails, and chatting), the findings suggest that individuals share knowledge through face-to-face dialogue and interact through technology mediated networks and these mechanisms have significant positive effect on the extent of knowledge sharing. Previous studies also suggest that informal face-to-face methods (such as storytelling, Hansen and Haas, 2001) and communication through technology networks are effective in sharing knowledge in project teams (e.g. Garrett and Caldwell, 2002; Hall, 2001; Jones and Borgman, 2007; Newell et al. 2006). However, the findings of our study suggest that although publications, seminars and workshops are mechanisms of sharing knowledge these do not have a significant impact on knowledge sharing. This may be due to the fact that these mechanisms are not oriented towards a problem a team member has at a particular moment (see Hansen and Haas, 2001). However, it should be noted that our review of literature has not been able to find any studies that addressed the influence of knowledge sharing mechanisms on knowledge sharing in the project team environment or software development industry, in particular. Therefore, more empirical studies are needed to broaden the understanding.

Knowledge sharing is a craving outcome sought by employers, especially, in project team context. Therefore, the findings presented in this paper would be valuable for academics and practitioners alike. On the one hand, the findings of our study contribute to the literature on knowledge sharing by examining widely accepted concepts to the context of project teams. It should be noted that there is surprisingly little empirical research addressing the influence of team leader support, interpersonal trust, rewards, and knowledge sharing mechanisms on the extent of knowledge sharing in project teams in a single study.

Therefore, more empirical work is needed to test our propositions and to replicate, extend, or disconfirm the results presented in this article. Therefore, we believe that the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area. On the other hand, practitioners need valid information to guide their actions in enhancing knowledge sharing in project teams. This becomes essential as the membership of project teams is typically assigned by management (see Blankenship and Ruona, 2009). As a project team typically stays together until the project or task is completed and then disbands the social structure for knowledge sharing is also temporary in nature. Therefore, any organisation that use project teams would be interested in members' sharing the knowledge during the course of accomplishing project tasks as well as sharing the knowledge that resided within the team members before it disbands to be used with new projects. The significant relationship between interpersonal trust and knowledge sharing suggests that organisations should pay more attention to the fit of team members selected for a project team and the types of orientation and socialisation programmes to be given to instil interpersonal trust as a project team has a finite lifespan. In this regard, Zakaria et al. (2004) suggest that trust needs to be imported, rather than developed. Further, the findings suggest that rewards system should be designed in such a way to send strong signals to individuals to share knowledge. Furthermore, the findings have implications for the existence and availability of various mechanisms to share knowledge between project team members. Knowledge sharing mechanisms link team members to others in the team thereby providing solutions to problems and support their individual knowledge development. The mechanisms generated in our analysis could be used to evaluate mechanisms which are used frequently and which are neglected as well as to determine mechanisms to be used to enhance knowledge sharing in project teams.

Limitations of the study and areas for future research

First, the study was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology; the study relied on self-reported data. On the one hand, survey method used in the study made

it difficult to obtain objective data for knowledge sharing without threatening the anonymity of the respondents. However, Yi (2009) and Newell et al. (2006) argue that although electronic-based knowledge sharing is relatively easier to track other forms of knowledge sharing such as those taking place through informal interactions are also important. On the other hand, future research studies in different samples that complimented questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data are necessary to validate the links proposed in this study. In such study designs questionnaire survey may provide access to breadth of experience while the interviews may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey. Further, although longitudinal research presents a distinctive set of challenges in exploring human related variables such studies may provide a deeper understanding. Second, we have taken individuals within project teams as our unit of analysis. Therefore, the characteristics of the broader organisation in which project teams operate are beyond the scope of the study. Third, we are unable to find previous empirical studies conducted on knowledge sharing in software development projects in Sri Lanka or in the South Asian context. Therefore, as an exploratory study we have not made a distinction between knowledge type (e.g. tacit and explicit) or rewards type (e.g. extrinsic or intrinsic). Future research could incorporate such distinctions. Future research could also incorporate the influence of other variables such as performance evaluations on knowledge sharing. Although one can argue that interrelationships exists between variables of the study such interrelationships are beyond the focus of this study and have not been explored as a result. Therefore, future research can incorporate such relationships with a larger sample and with more sophisticated data analysis techniques such as structural equation modelling.

References

Al-Alawi, A.I., Al-Marzooqi, N.Y. and Mohammed, Y.F. (2007), "Organizational culture and knowledge sharing: critical success factors", *Journal of Knowledge Management*, Vol. 11 No. 2, pp. 22-42

Andrews, K.M. and Delahaye, B.L. (2000), "Influences on knowledge processes in organizational learning: the psychosocial filter", *Journal of Management Studies* Vol. 37 No. 6, pp. 797–810.

Bain, P.G., Mann, L., Atkins, L. and Dunning, J. (2005), "R&D Project Leaders: Roles and Responsibilities", in L. Mann (ed.) *Leadership, Management, and Innovation in R&D Project Teams*, pp. 49–70. Westport, CT: Praeger.

Barry, D. (1991), "Managing the bossless team: lessons in distributed leadership", *Organizational Dynamics*, Vol. 20 No. 1, pp. 31–47.

Bartol, K.M. and Locke, E.A. (2000), "Incentives and motivation", In: S. Rynes and B. Gerhardt (eds), *Compensation in Organization: Progress and Prospects*, pp. 104–47. Lexington Press, San Francisco, CA.

Bartol, K.M. and Srivastava, A. (2002), "Encouraging knowledge sharing: the role of organizational reward systems", *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 64-77.

Bennis, W.G. and Townsend, R. (1997), "Reinventing leadership: strategies to empower the organization", New York: Morrow/Avon.

Berends, H., van der Bij, H., Debackere, K. and Weggeman, M. (2006), "Knowledge sharing mechanisms in industrial research", *R&D Management*, Vol. 36 No. 1, pp. 85-95.

Bernhardt, N. and Ragsdell, G. (2006), "Exploring the relationship between collaboration, trust and knowledge sharing: a case study from the air-conditioning industry", *OR Insight*, Vol. 19 No. 1, pp. 9-17.

Blankenship S.S. and Ruona, W.E.A. (2009), "Exploring knowledge sharing in social structures: potential contributions to an overall knowledge management strategy", *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, Vol. 11 No. 3, pp. 290-306.

Bock, G-W., Zmud, R.W., Kim, Y-G. and Lee, J-N. (2005), "Behavioral intention formation in knowledge sharing: examining the roles of extrinsic motivators, social-psychological forces, and organizational climate", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 29 No. 1. pp. 87-111.

Bresnen, M., Edelman, L., Newell, S., Scarbrough, H., and Swan, J. (2003), "Social Practices and the Management of Knowledge in Project Environments," *International Journal of Project Management* ,21, pp. 157-166.

Cabrera, E.F. and Cabrera, A. (2005), "Fostering knowledge sharing through people management practices", *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 16 No. 5, pp. 720-735.

Choi, S.Y., Kang, Y.S. and Lee, H. (2008), "The effects of socio-technical enablers on knowledge sharing: an exploratory examination", *Journal of Information Science*, Vol. 34 No. 5, pp. 742–754.

Cohen, S.G. and Bailey, D.E. (1997), "What makes team work: group effectiveness research from the shop floor to the executive suite", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 23 No. 3, pp. 239–390.

Cook, J. and Wall, T. (1980), "New Work Attitude Measures of Trust, Organizational Commitment and Personal Need Non-Fulfilment", *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, Vol. 53, pp. 39–52.

Costa, A.C., Roe, R.A. and Taillieu, T. (2001), "Trust within teams: the relation with performance effectiveness", *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, Vol. 10 No. 3, pp. 225-244.

Cronk, L. and Ragsdell, G. (2008), "Knowledge sharing by micro-teams: a case study in an information services department" *OR Insight*, Vol. 21 No. 4, pp. 19-27.

Davenport, T.H. (1997). *Information ecology*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.

Department of Census and Statistics (2008), *Sri Lanka Labour Force Survey Final Report – 2007*. Department of Census and Statistics, Colombo, Sri Lanka.

Eppler, M.J. and Sukowski, O. (2000), "Managing team knowledge: core processes, tools and enabling factors", *European Management Journal*, Vol. 18 No. 3, pp. 334–241.

Faraj, S. and Sproull, L. (2000), "Coordinating expertise in software development teams", *Management Science*, Vol. 46, pp. 1554–1568.

Fong, P.S. and Chu, L. (2006), "Exploratory study of knowledge sharing in contracting companies: a sociotechnical perspective", *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, September, pp. 928-939.

Friesl, M., Sackmann, S.A. and Kremser, S. (2011), "Knowledge sharing in new organizational entities: The impact of hierarchy, organizational context, micro-politics and suspicion", *Cross Cultural Management: An International Journal*, Vol. 18 No. 1, pp. 71-86.

Fukuyama, F. (1995), *Trust: the social virtues and the creation of prosperity*. The Free Press, New York.

Garrett, S. and Caldwell, B. (2002), "Describing functional requirements for knowledge sharing communities", *Behaviour and Information Technology*, Vol. 21, No. 5, pp. 359-364

Gupta, A.K. and Govindarajan, V. (2000), "Knowledge management social dimension: lessons from Nucor Steel", *Sloan Management Review*, Vol. 42 No. 1, pp. 71-81.

Hall, H. (2001), "Input-friendliness: motivating knowledge sharing across intranets", *Journal of Information Science*, Vol. 27 No. 3, pp. 139–146.

Hansen, M.T. and Haas, M.R. (2001), "Competing for attention in knowledge markets", *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 46 No. 1, pp. 1–28.

- Holste J.S. and Fields, D. (2010), "Trust and tacit knowledge sharing and use", *Journal of Knowledge Management*, Vol. 14 No. 1, pp. 128-140.
- Huang, J.C. and Newell, S. (2003), "Knowledge integration processes and dynamics within the context of cross-functional projects", *International Journal of Project Management*, Vol. 21 No. 3, pp. 167–176.
- Ipe, M. (2003), "Knowledge sharing in organizations: a conceptual framework", *Human Resource Development Review*, Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 337-359.
- Jewels, T. and Ford, M. (2006), "Factors Influencing Knowledge Sharing in Information Technology Projects", *e-Service Journal*, pp 99-117.
- Jones, N.B. and Borgman, R.H. (2007), "An exploratory study on knowledge sharing, information technologies and firm performance", *OR Insight*, Vol. 20 No. 4, pp. 10-21.
- Kim, S. and Lee, H. (2006), "The impact of organizational context and information technology on employee knowledge-sharing capabilities", *Public Administration Review*, May-June, pp. 370-385.
- Kotlarsky, J., Oshri, I., van Hillegersberg, J. and Kumar, K. (2007), "Globally distributed component-based software development: an exploratory study of knowledge management and work division", *Journal of Information Technology*, Vol. 22, pp. 161–173.
- Kramer, R.M. (1999), "Trust and distrust in organizations: emerging perspectives, enduring questions", *Annual Review of Psychology*, Vol. 50, pp. 569-598.
- Kramer, R.M. and Lewicki, R.J. (2010), "Repairing and enhancing trust: approaches to reducing organizational trust deficits", *The Academy of Management Annals*, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp. 245–277.
- Kraut, R.E. and Streeter, L.A. (1995), "Coordination in software development", *Communications of ACM*, Vol. 38, pp. 69-81.
- Lam, A. (2000), "Tacit knowledge, organizational learning and societal institutions: An integrated framework", *Organization Studies*, Vol. 21 No. 3, pp. 487-513.
- Lee, J. (2001), "The impact of knowledge sharing, organizational capability and partnership quality on IS outsourcing success", *Information & Management*, Vol. 38 No. 5, pp. 323–335.
- Lee, P., Gillespie, N., Mann, L. and Wearing, A. (2010), "Leadership and trust: their effect on knowledge sharing and team performance", *Management Learning*, Vol. 41 No. 4, pp. 473-491.
- Leinonen, P. and Bluemink, J. (2008), "The distributed team members' explanations of knowledge they assume to be shared", *Journal of Workplace Learning*, Vol. 20 No. 1, pp. 38-53.

Liebowitz, J. (2002), "Facilitating innovation through knowledge sharing: a look at the U.S. Naval surface warfare center-carderock division", *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, Vol. 42 No. 5, pp. 1–6.

Lin, C-P. (2008), "Clarifying the relationship between organizational citizenship behaviors, gender, and knowledge sharing in workplace organizations in Taiwan", *Journal of Business Psychology*, Vol. 22, pp. 241–250.

Lin, H-F. (2006), "Impact of organizational support on organizational intention to facilitate knowledge sharing", *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*, Vol. 4, pp. 26–35.

Lin, H-F. (2007), "Effects of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on employee knowledge sharing intentions", *Journal of Information Science*, Vol. 33 No. 2, pp. 135–149.

Lowendahl, B.R., Revang, O. And Fosstenlokken, S.M. (2001), "Knowledge and value creation in professional service firms: a framework for analysis", *Human Relations*, Vol. 54 No. 7, pp. 911-931.

MacNeil, C.M. (2003), "Line managers: facilitators of knowledge sharing in teams", *Employee Relations*, Vol. 25 No. 3, pp. 294-307.

Mayer, R.C., Davis, J.H. and Schoorman, F.D. (1995), "An integrative model of organisational trust", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 20 No. 3, pp.709–734.

McAllister, D.J. (1995), "Affect- and cognition-based trust as foundations for interpersonal cooperation in organizations", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 38 No. 1, pp. 24-59.

McDermott, R. and O'Dell, C. (2001), "Overcoming cultural barriers to sharing knowledge", *Journal of Knowledge Management*, Vol. 5 No. 1, pp. 76-85.

Mitchell, T.R., Holtom, B.C. and Lee, T.W. (2001), "How to keep your best employees: developing an effective retention policy", *Academy of Management Executive*, Vol. 15 No. 4, pp. 96-109.

Mooradian, T., Renzl, B. and Matzler, K. (2006), "Who trusts? personality, trust and knowledge sharing", *Management Learning*, Vol. Vol. 37 No. 4, pp. 523–540.

Newell, S., Bresnen, M., Edelman, L., Scarbrough, H. and Swan, J. (2006), "Sharing knowledge across projects: limits to ICT-led project review practices", *Management Learning* Vol. 37 No. 2, pp. 167–85.

Nidumolu, S. (1995), "The effect of coordination and uncertainty on software project performance: residual performance risk as an intervening variable", *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 6, pp. 191-219.

Nonaka, I. (1990), "Redundant, overlapping organization: a Japanese approach to managing the innovation process", *California Management Review*, Vol. 32 No. 3, pp. 27-38.

- Nonaka, I. and Takeuchi, H. (1995), *The Knowledge-creating Company: how Japanese companies create the dynamics of innovation*. Oxford University Press, New York, NY.
- O'Neill, B.S. and Adya, M. (2007), "Knowledge sharing and the psychological contract-managing knowledge workers across different stages of employment", *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, Vol. 22 No. 4, 2007 pp. 411-436.
- Podsakoff, P., MacKenzie, S., Lee, J-Y. and Podsakoff, N., (2003), "Common method biases in behavioral research: a critical review of the literature and recommended remedies", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 88 No. 5, pp. 879-903.
- Refaiy, M. and Labib, A. (2009), "The effect of applying tacit knowledge on maintenance performance: an empirical study of the energy sector in the UK and Arab countries", *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*, Vol. 7, pp. 77–288.
- Renzi, B. (2008), "Trust in management and knowledge sharing: the mediating effects of fear and knowledge documentation", *International Journal of Management Science*, Vol. 36 No. 2, pp. 206–220.
- Reychav, I. and Weisberg, J. (2010), "Bridging intention and behavior of knowledge sharing", *Journal of Knowledge Management*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 285-300.
- Rivera-Vazquez, J.C., Ortiz-Fournier, L.V. and Flores, F.R. (2009), "Overcoming cultural barriers for innovation and knowledge sharing", *Journal of Knowledge Management*, Vol. 13 No. 5, pp. 257-270.
- Ruuska, I. and Vartiainen, M. (2005), "Characteristics of knowledge sharing communities in project organizations", *International Journal of Project Management*, Vol. 23 No. 5, pp. 374-379.
- Scholarios, D. and Marks, A. (2004), "Work-life balance and the software worker", *Human Resource Management Journal*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 54-74.
- SLICTA (2007), *Rising demand: the increasing demand for IT workers spells a challenging opportunity for the IT industry-National IT workforce survey*, Sri Lanka ICT Association, Colombo.
- Small, C.T. and Sage, A.P. (2006), "Knowledge management and knowledge sharing: a review", *Information Knowledge Systems Management*, Vol. 5, pp. 153–169.
- Spector, P.E. (1994), "Using self-report questionnaires in OB research: a comment on the use of a controversial method", *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 15 No. 5, pp. 385-392.
- Srivastava, A., Bartol, K.M. and Locke, E.A. (2006), "Empowering leadership in management teams: effects on knowledge sharing, efficacy, and performance", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 49 No. 6, pp. 1239–1251.

- Staples, S.D. and Jarvenpaa, S.L. (2001), "Exploring perceptions of organizational ownership of information and expertise", *Journal of Management Information Systems*, Vol. 18 No. 1, pp. 151-183.
- Szulanski, G. (1996), "Exploring internal stickiness: impediments to the transfer of best practice within the firm", *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 17 Winter Special Issue, pp. 27-43.
- Taylor, E.Z. (2006), "The effect of incentives on knowledge sharing in computer-mediated communication: an experimental investigation", *Journal of Information Systems*, Vol. 20 No. 1, pp. 103-116.
- Teng, J.T.C. and Song, S. (2011) "An Exploratory Examination of Knowledge Sharing Behaviors: Solicited and Voluntary", *Journal of Knowledge Management*, Vol. 15 No. 1, pp. 104-117.
- Walsham, G. (2001), Knowledge management: the benefits and limitations of computer systems. *European Management Journal*, Vol. 19 No. 6, pp. 599-608.
- Walz, D.B., Elam, J.J. and Curtis, B. (1993), "Inside a software design team: knowledge acquisition, sharing, and integration", *Communications of ACM*, Vol. 36, pp. 63-77.
- Weick, K.E. and Roberts, K.H. (1993), "Collective mind in organizations: heedful interrelating on flight decks", *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 38 No. 3, pp. 357-381.
- Weiss, L. (1999), "Collection and connection: the anatomy of knowledge sharing in professional service", *Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 17 No. 4, pp. 61-72.
- Wenger, E.C. and Snyder, W.M. (2000), "Communities of practice: the organizational frontier", *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 78 No. 1, pp. 139-145.
- Whitener, E.M., Brodt, S.E., Korsgaard, M.A. and Werner, J.M. (1998), "Managers as initiators of trust: an exchange relationship framework for understanding managerial trustworthy behaviour", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 23 No. 3, pp. 513-531.
- Wolfe, C. and Loraas, T. (2008), "Knowledge sharing: the effects of incentives, environment, and person", *Journal of Information Systems*, Vol. 22 No. 2, pp. 53-76.
- Yi, J. (2009), "A measure of knowledge sharing behavior: scale development and validation", *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*, Vol. 7, pp. 65-81.
- Za'rraga, C. and Bonache, J. (2003), "Assessing the team environment for knowledge sharing: an empirical analysis", *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 14 No. 7, pp. 1227-1245.
- Zakaria, N., Amelinckx, A. and Wilemon, D. (2004), "Working together apart? building a knowledge-sharing culture for global virtual teams", *Creativity and Innovation Management*, Vol. 13 No.1, pp. 15-29.

Zand, D.E. (1972), "Trust and managerial problem solving", *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 17 No. 2, pp. 229–239.

Figure

Figure 1: Research model

Tables

Table I: Characteristics of the sample

Age (in years):	
Mean	30
Median	29
S.D.	3.17
Skewness	1.75
Kurtosis	2.53
Sex (%):	
Male	70
Female	30
The highest level of qualification (%):	
Bachelor's degree or equivalent Professional qualifications [†]	80
Postgraduate degree [‡]	20
Tenure in the present firm (in years):	
Mean	3.91
Median	3.5
S.D.	2.74
Skewness	1.56
Kurtosis	1.43
Tenure in the industry (in years):	
Mean	5.42
Median	4.0
S.D.	4.15
Skewness	2.65
Kurtosis	3.54
Number of team members:	
Mean	8.93
Median	7.67
S.D.	3.12
Skewness	1.07
Kurtosis	.45
Number of employees in the firm (%):	
500 or less= 0	22
more than 500	78
Years of industry presence:	
Mean	12.27
Median	12.00
S.D.	8.32
Skewness	2.75
Kurtosis	3.70

Note: N=150

S.D.= standard deviation

[†] Membership in British Computer Society, Australian Computer Society, and Project Management Professional.

[‡] MSc in information Technology, MSc in Computer Science, and Master of Business Administration (MBA) specialised in Information Technology, MBA specialised in Management of Technology, and MBA (general).

Table II: Factor analysis - knowledge sharing mechanisms in use

	Mean	S.D.	F1 Work-group communications	F2 Personal interactions	F3 Publications, seminars & workshops
Group discussions and information pooling	3.77	.83	.637		
Social bookmarking	3.92	.93	.616		
Document management	3.02	.97	.589		
Brainstorming and collective problem solving	4.62	.91	.537		
Internet search	4.42	.84		.644	
Wikis	4.40	.86		.593	
Informal chatting and story telling	4.19	.85		.550	
E-mails	3.91	.62		.542	
Discussion forums	3.51	1.10		.517	
Chat rooms	3.93	1.01		.510	
Internal technical documents and case studies of past projects from the intranet	3.48	.67			.663
Seminars	2.49	1.03			.653
Workshops	2.31	1.05			.556
Explained variation			39.29%	22.48%	11.18%
Eigenvalue			4.06	2.01	1.19
Standardised Cronbach's alpha			.742	.763	.796

Table III: Correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1 Age ^a	3.35	.13	1											
2 Gender ^b	.27	.44	-.086	1										
3 Tenure ^a	1.16	.65	.593**	-.034	1									
4 No. of team members ^a	1.46	.67	.458**	-.164	.350**	1								
5 No. of employees ^b	.81	.39	.008	.123	.329**	.053	1							
6 Yrs of industry presence ^a	2.44	.35	.092	.019	.141	.001	.344**	1						
7 Interpersonal trust	4.00	.52	.072	.182*	.005	.031	.022	.005	1					
8 Rewards	3.04	.82	-.017	.135	-.040	-.019	.020	.111	.110	1				
9 Team leader support	3.70	.87	-.125	.042	-.153	-.155	.159	.041	.167*	.083	1			
10 Work-group communications	3.64	.65	.035	.321**	.005	.100	.190*	.030	.299**	.147	.165*	1		
11 Personal interactions Publications,	4.20	.59	.056	.187*	.006	.073	.194*	.027	.388**	.082	.137	.317**	1	
12 seminars & workshops	3.08	.64	-.005	.161*	.066	.042	.060	.063	.231**	.141	.124	.301**	.304**	1
13 Knowledge sharing	4.17	.53	.074	.154*	.066	.002	.097	.001	.568**	.269**	.198	.436**	.352**	.146

Notes: ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

^a Log transformed

^b Binary-coded variables

Table IV: Summarized results - regression analysis

Step	Variable	β	R^2	R^2 (Adj.)	Change statistics		
					R^2 Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change
1	Age	.042	.091	.048	.091	1.954	.058
	Gender	.107					
	Tenure	.116					
	No. of team members	.076					
	No. of employees	-.067					
	Yrs of industry presence	.008					
2	Age	.076	.515	.466***	.424	17.479	.000
	Gender	.095					
	Tenure	.090					
	No. of team members	.039					
	No. of employees	-.011					
	Yrs of industry presence	.003					
	Interpersonal trust	.493***					
	Rewards	.269*					
	Team leader support	.144					
	Work-group communications	.294**					
	Personal interactions	.169*					
	Publications, seminars & workshops	.103					

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.